

**11-year solar activity cycle and the US GDP index (1948 – 2025): R2=1.0
(SA growth phase), R2=0.99 (SA decline phase)
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Abstract

This paper uses a methodological approach developed by W.S. Jevonson and A.L. Chizhevsky. The years of the solar cycle were numbered in the order established in solar astrophysics and compared with the average values of the US GDP indices and Wolf numbers. The determination coefficient R2 on the Wolf number diagram for the US GDP index in the CA growth phase (years 1–4 of cycles, 29 years of observation) was 1.0, while in the decline phase (years 4–11 of cycles, 55 years of observation) it was 0.99.

The diagram data shows the minimum values of the US GDP indices in the region of extremes (maximums and minimums) of the Wolf numbers.

A three-zone neuroendocrine model of the cyclical dynamics of US GDP has been developed.

1. "Biological depression" zone (Wolf number (W) < 20): A deficiency of ultraviolet radiation leads to a decrease in serotonin levels, creating a mood of pessimism and stagnation of US GDP.

2. "Biological optimum" zone (W = 20–130): Sufficient levels of serotonin and melatonin ensure optimism and peak growth rates of US GDP with a lag of 1 year.

3. "Biological Stress" Zone (W > 130): Extreme solar activity suppresses melatonin production (according to R. Reiter's concept), causing "exhaustion pessimism," a decline in consumer and investment activity, and a sharp decline in US GDP growth.

The identified relationships allow us to predict the US GDP index. With a predicted 2026 Wolf number of 93.76, the predicted US GDP for 2026 is 3.33%.

Keywords: solar activity cycle, Wolf numbers, economic crises, economic cycles, US GDP, economic forecasting

The IMF, in its World Economic Outlook of January 9, 2020, noted that "Global growth is projected to decline from 2.9 percent in 2019 to 3.3 percent in 2020..." [1]. This fact is a clear illustration of the state of affairs with traditional economic theory and forecasting theory.

In issue №2 of the journal "Society and Power" for 2013, my article "Cosmic Factors of Economic Cycles" was published, concluding with a forecast of the 2020 economic crisis [2]. This forecast was based on the forecast of the minimum solar activity (SA) of its 24th cycle.

Great scientists Frederick William Herschel, William Stanley Jevons, and Alexander Leonidovich Chizhevsky developed a methodological approach to studying the connections between solar and economic activity in their works.

For example, in his article "Solar-Commercial Cycles" W. S. Jevons placed graphs of solar activity cycles (Wolf number cycles) and corn price cycles in Delhi

over the period 1760-1810 one after the other [3, p.227]. That is, he compared solar and economic activity.

A. L. Chizhevsky in his monograph “The Cosmic Pulse of Life: Earth in the Embrace of the Sun” in Chapter 4 “The Sun and Epidemics” in Fig. 33 constructed a diagram that depicts the average solar activity (SA) cycle (Wolf number cycle) over a hundred years and the average number of cholera cases in Russia for the period 1823-1923 [4, p. 201]. That is, he used the method of superimposing eras.

In this study, a single diagram compares the years of the average solar cycle in order depending on the value of the average annual Wolf numbers, as well as the average US GDP indices and average Wolf numbers.

The annual mean Wolf numbers (W), the main indicator of solar activity, were taken from the well-known astrophysical website for the determination, conservation, and distribution of the international sunspot number [5]. They are presented in column 2 of Table 1.

The year numbers in column 3 of Table 1 are determined in accordance with the year numbering conventions used in solar astrophysics. Specifically, the first year in a solar cycle is considered to be the first year of its growth, i.e., the increase in the Wolf number. Subsequent years are numbered sequentially, and the last year in the cycle is considered to be the year of the Wolf number minimum.

The seasonally adjusted annual percentage changes in real US GDP for the period 1948–2025 were obtained from the website “Economic Research. Federal Reserve Bank. St. Louis” [6] and are presented in column 4 of Table 1.

Table 1. Years, average annual Wolf numbers, ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles and US GDP indices (1948-2025)

Year	Wolf Number	Year Order in Solar Cycle	Real US GDP Growth Index, %
1	2	3	4
1948	193.0	4	4.12
1949	190.7	5	-0.56
1950	118.9	6	8.69
1951	98.3	7	8.04
1952	45.0	8	4.08
1953	20.1	9	4.69
1954	6.6	10	-0.58

1955	54.2	1	7.13
1956	200.7	2	2.13
1957	269.3	3	2.11
1958	261.7	4	-0.74
1959	225.1	5	6.93
1960	159.0	6	2.57
1961	76.4	7	2.57
1962	53.4	8	6.13
1963	39.9	9	4.36
1964	15.0	10	5.76
1965	22.0	1	6.50
1966	66.8	2	6.60
1967	132.9	3	2.74
1968	150.0	4	4.91
1969	149.4	5	3.12
1970	148.0	6	0.18
1971	94.4	7	3.29
1972	97.6	8	5.26
1973	54.1	9	5.65
1974	49.2	10	-0.54
1975	22.5	11	-0.21
1976	18.4	12	5.39
1977	39.3	1	4.62
1978	131.0	2	5.54

1979	220.1	3	3.17
1980	218.9	4	-0.26
1981	198.9	5	2.54
1982	162.4	6	-1.80
1983	91.0	7	4.58
1984	60.5	8	7.24
1985	20.6	9	4.17
1986	14.8	10	3.46
1987	33.9	1	3.45
1988	123.0	2	4.18
1989	211.1	3	3.67
1990	191.8	4	1.89
1991	203.3	5	-0.11
1992	133.0	6	3.52
1993	76.1	7	2.75
1994	44.9	8	4.03
1995	25.1	9	2.68
1996	11.6	10	3.77
1997	28.9	1	4.45
1998	88.3	2	4.48
1999	136.3	3	4.79
2000	173.9	4	4.08
2001	170.4	5	0.96
2002	163.6	6	1.70

2003	99.3	7	2.80
2004	65.3	8	3.85
2005	45.8	9	3.48
2006	24.7	10	2.78
2007	12.6	11	2.00
2008	4.2	12	0.11
2009	4.8	1	-2.58
2010	24.9	2	2.70
2011	80.8	3	1.56
2012	84.5	4	2.29
2013	94.0	5	2.12
2014	113.3	6	2.52
2015	69.8	7	2.95
2016	39.8	8	1.82
2017	21.7	9	2.46
2018	7.0	10	2.97
2019	3.6	11	2.58
2020	8.8	1	-2.08
2021	29.6	2	6.15
2022	83.2	3	2.52
2023	125.5	4	2.93
2024	154.7	5	2.79
2025	123.2	6	2.11
2026		7	

The statistical data in Table 1 were then grouped by the ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles. The results of this grouping are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Grouping of data from Table 1 by ordinal numbers of years in the SA cycles

1. The ordinal number of the year in the SA cycle	Number of years with this order number for the period 1948–2025	Arithmetic mean:		5. Ratio to the previous year's US real GDP index
		3. Wolf numbers	4. US real GDP index, %	
1	7	27.41	3.07	1.12
2	7	94.90	4.54	1.48
3	7	161.96	2.94	0.65
4	8	174.91	2.40	0.82
5	8	173.31	2.22	0.93
6	8	140.18	2.44	1.10
7	7	86.47	3.85	1.58
8	7	58.07	4.63	1.20
9	7	32.47	3.93	0.85
10	7	18.41	2.52	0.64
11	3	12.90	1.46	0.58
12	2	11.30	2.75	1.88
Итого:	78			

Based on the data in rows 1–4 (CA growth) and columns 3 and 4 of Table 2, a diagram was constructed (see Fig. 1), which shows a strong connection between the average US GDP indices and Wolf numbers in this segment of the average (12 years) solar cycle for 1948–2025.

Fig. 1. Very strong relationship between average US GDP indices and Wolf numbers, years 1–4 (SA growth phase) for 1948–2025, 29 years of observations, overlapping eras method

The value of the approximation coefficient R^2 equal to 1.0 means that the model developed in Fig. 1 is well suited for predicting the value of the dependent variable (US GDP index) based on the independent variable (Wolf number) for years 1–4 of the SA cycles.

Changes in US GDP over this period (years 1–4 of SA growth) are 100% explained by the model in Figure 1. Random factors such as Fed actions or foreign policy, according to this chart, either had no effect on the outcome or their effect was strictly proportional to the solar cycle.

Based on the data in rows 4–12 and columns 3 and 4 of Table 2, the following diagram (see Fig. 2) was constructed, which shows a strong relationship between the average US GDP indices and the Wolf numbers in this segment of the decline in the CA for 1948–2025. R^2 in this graph is equal to 0.8484. This means that the model explains only 85% of the changes in GDP, while 15% is accounted for by other factors.

Fig. 2. Strong correlation between average Wolf numbers and US GDP indices for 4-12 years of SA decline over 1948-2025, 57 years of observations, overlapping eras method

Over the entire observation period (78 years), there were only two solar cycle years with the number 12. That is, there were only two 12-year cycles. The solar cycle is also called the 11-year cycle, since its average duration is 11 years. If we exclude years numbered 12 from the diagram in Figure 2, we obtain a diagram with an extremely high determination coefficient R^2 of 0.9964 (see Figure 3).

This means that 99.64% of US GDP dynamics are explained by changes in the SA (Wolf numbers) during its downward phase. Less than 0.4% is left for "noise" and all other factors (politics, taxes, wars, pandemics, etc.).

Fig. 3. Average Wolf numbers and US GDP indices, 4–11 years of cycles (CA decline phase) for the period 1948–2025, 55 years of observations, overlapping eras method

The ordinal number of 2026 is 7 (see Table 1). Therefore, the model in Figure 3 is suitable for forecasting US GDP in 2026. This requires knowing the forecast value of the Wolf number for 2026.

The predicted value of the Wolf number can be calculated based on data from the NASA website [7]. It is defined as the average monthly value of SUNSPOT NUMBERS PERCENTILE 50% for January–December 2026 and is equal to 93.76. This Wolf number in the diagram in Fig. 3 corresponds to the predicted value of the US GDP index equal to 3.55%.

Another forecasting method is based on the US GDP index for the previous year, 2025 (year 6 of the SA cycle, the index is 2.11) and the ratio of the GDP indices for year 7 to those for year 6 (see Table 2). That is, the forecast US GDP index is $2.11 * 1.58 = 3.33\%$.

Based on rows 1–12 and columns 3 and 4 of Table 2, Figure 4 shows a strong correlation between the average Wolf numbers and US GDP indices for all 12 years of the average solar cycle from 1948 to 2025. The coefficient of determination in this diagram, R^2 , is 0.8034. This is a strong correlation. Mathematically, this means that solar activity (through a biochemical mechanism) explains more than 80% of the variation in US GDP growth rates over the past 78 years.

Fig. 4. Strong correlation between Wolf numbers and US GDP indices, 12 years of SA cycles for 1948–2025, 78 years of observations, overlapping eras method

If we exclude the 2 years with numbers 12 from the diagram in Fig. 4, we obtain a diagram with a significantly higher value of the R2 coefficient, namely 0.9105 (see Fig. 5).

The value of 0.91 suggests that the solar cycle explains more than 91% of all the changes in US GDP over the 76 years in this chart.

Fig. 5. Average Wolf numbers and US GDP indices, 11 years of SA cycles for 1948–2025, 76 years of observations, overlapping eras method

It's interesting to note that the US GDP graph in Figure 5 resembles a solar cycle in shape. Three distinct zones are clearly visible in this main diagram.

1. The “biological depression” zone ($W < 20$): A deficiency of ultraviolet radiation leads to a decrease in serotonin levels, creating a mood of pessimism and stagnation of US GDP.

2. The "biological optimum" zone ($W = 20 - 130$): A sufficient level of the ultraviolet index and, as a consequence, serotonin and melatonin ensures optimistic moods and peak growth rates of US GDP.

3. The "biological stress" zone ($W > 130$): Extreme solar activity suppresses the production of melatonin (according to the concept of R. Reiter [8]), causing "exhaustion pessimism", a decrease in consumer and investment activity, and a sharp decline in the rate of US GDP.

Thus, a three-zone neuroendocrine model of the cyclical dynamics of GDP has been developed.

PhD Igor Nikulin, senior researcher at the Sternberg Astronomical Institute, notes in an interview with Rossiyskaya Gazeta that “over millions of years of evolution, all living beings have adapted to the average values of these factors [temperature, pressure, atmospheric composition, magnetic field – V.B.], and even small deviations in one direction or another negatively affect their vital functions” [9]. The diagrams in Figs. 4 and 5 show that the human body has adapted to the average values of the main SA indicator – the Wolf number.

Based on the data in columns 1, 3, and 4 of Table 2, the following diagram (see Fig. 6) was constructed, which demonstrates a strong correlation between the average cycle indexes of the SA and the US real GDP indices. The approximation coefficient in this diagram is 0.96.

Fig. 6. Average solar and economic (US GDP), 12-year solar cycles, 1948–2025, 78 years of observations

If we remove 2 years with numbers 12 from the diagram in Fig. 6, it will take the form shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Average solar and economic (US GDP), 11-year solar cycles, 1948–2025, 76 years of observations

A crucial question arises: "What about military-political events, sanctions, trade wars, and epidemics with determination coefficients of 1.0 and 0.99?" It turns out that even such gigantic events as COVID-19 and others, in annualized terms, merely "fit" into a predetermined curve for US GDP and were themselves part of the SA cycle, which confirms A.L. Chizhevsky's theory.

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